

Study of Electro-Reduction and Kinetics of Electrode Reaction of Praseodymium(III) in Potassium Chloride at a Dropping Mercury Cathode

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Polarographic reduction of Pr(III) in KCl + 0.01% gelatin at pH 2.4 ± 0.02 has been investigated. The concentration of supporting electrolyte affects the nature of the reduction wave. On polarographing Pr(III) in 0.1 M to 0.4 M KCl at pH 2.4 ± 0.02 in presence of 0.01% gelatin, an irreversible polarographic wave is observed, which tends to become quasi-reversible with increasing concentration of the supporting electrolyte and finally attains almost reversible nature in 1.0 M KCl. Pr(III) gives a well defined reversible three-electron reduction wave at pH 2.2-3.2 which is of diffusion controlled nature. The half wave potential is independent of the metal ion concentration while the diffusion current is proportional to the metal ion concentration. A shift in the half wave potential to more negative value is observed with decreasing pH of the test solution.

THE first polarographic study of rare earth elements was made by Noddack and Brukl¹, who studied the polarographic reduction of rare earths sulphate without any supporting electrolyte. In all the cases they observed an incompletely separated double wave which was attributed to stepwise reduction to +2 state and finally to the metals. Swenson and Glockler² also studied the polarographic reduction of Pr(III) in lithium chloride and tetramethylammonium iodide in which the half wave potential was shown to drift with change in metal ion concentration. Misumi and Aihara³ reported the electro-reduction of Pr(III) and Nd(III) by cyclic-volta-metric technique. The use of increasing concentration of supporting electrolyte on the polarographic reduction and kinetics of electrode reaction of various depolarizers was reported by many workers⁴⁻⁸. The present authors reported the polarographic reduction of Ce(III) and Nd(III) in 0.1 M to 1.0 M potassium chloride at a lower pH^{9,10}, in which well defined reversible reduction wave of each metal was observed. Lavale and Pitre recently reported the electro-reduction of Sm(III) in KCl¹¹. However, the literature is silent about the polarographic reduction and kinetics of electrode reaction of Pr(III) in KCl. The present communication deals with the polarographic reduction vis-a-vis kinetics of electrode reaction of Pr(III) in KCl as supporting electrolyte and gelatin as maximum suppressor at a relatively lower pH of 2.4 ± 0.02 .

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The solutions were prepared as reported earlier^{9,10}. A preliminary experimental set was prepared by keeping overall concentration of the metal ion,

supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor fixed at 2 mM Pr(III), 0.1 M KCl and 0.01% gelatin, respectively. The pH of the test solution was adjusted with hydrochloric acid/sodium hydroxide solutions and was measured with an Elico digital pH meter (Model LI-120). Dissolved oxygen was removed by passing pure nitrogen gas through the test solutions before recording the polarograms. An automatic pen recording polarograph (C.I.C. Baroda, India) was used to record the polarograms. The capillary used had a m value of 2.37 mg sec^{-1} at a drop time t of 3.0 second in an air-free 1.0 M potassium chloride at 35 cm effective height of the mercury column ($m^{2/3}t^{1/3} = 2.136 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/3}$). All measurements were made at room temperature (25 ± 1). A series of polarograms were recorded to study the effects of pH, supporting electrolyte concentration, metal ion concentration and gelatin on the polarographic behaviour including electrode kinetics of the depolarizer in varying experimental conditions.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH: The pH of the test solution played an important role in the polarographic reduction of Pr(III) in potassium chloride. At pH above 5.2 precipitation of the test solution was observed, which may be due to the decreased solubility of the compound at this pH. But on decreasing the pH to 3.3, a single reduction wave was observed with $E_{1/2} = -1.73 \text{ V vs SCE}$. The nature of this wave was not reproducible. On further decreasing the pH to 2.2, the reduction wave attained a well defined nature and the results were reproducible. The half wave potential shifted to more negative value with decreasing pH. This

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may be due to the formation of aquo complexes as reported earlier^{3,8}. Below pH 2.2, the nature of this reduction wave became distorted. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH ON HALF WAVE POTENTIAL AND DIFFUSION CURRENT CONSTANT OF 2 mM Pr(III) IN 0.1 M KCl+0.01% GELATIN

pH	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	i_d/C $\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}/\text{lit}$	I $\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}/\text{lit mg}^{2/3}\text{t}^{1/3}$
1.90		Distorted wave	
2.07		Poor limiting current	
2.20	1.84	6.8	3.19
2.42	1.81	7.4	3.46
2.63	1.80	8.4	3.93
2.80	1.78	7.2	3.37
3.02	1.76	7.0	3.27
3.20	1.74	7.1	3.32
3.75	1.73	—	—
4.50	1.73	—	—

However, the polarograms were very well defined between pH 2.20 to 3.20. The selection of pH value of 2.4 ± 0.02 was favoured, because at this pH the limiting current of the polarogram was nearly parallel to the residual current, so that the half wave potential and wave height could be measured more accurately, which was not observed in other supporting electrolytes². In the absence of gelatin, polarographic maxima was observed which was suppressed by 0.01% gelatin.

Effect of potassium chloride: Pr(III) in varying concentrations of KCl (0.1 M to 1.0 M) in the pH range of 2.2 to 3.2 showed a single well defined reduction wave. The number of electrons involved in the reduction process was determined by mill coulometric method of De Vries and Kroon¹⁹. In the present system, the charge number of the reaction (n) was observed to be 3. Knowing the value of (n) the diffusion coefficient was calculated by Ilkovic equation¹⁴ at different concentrations of potassium chloride, and are listed in Table 2.

The plots of $\log [i/(i_a - i)]$ vs E_{d_0} for each polarogram was similar, but the slope value decreased from 45 mV to 19 mV on subsequent increase of the supporting electrolyte. A decrease in the log plot slope value from 45 mV to 19 mV also confirmed that the electrode process tended towards reversibility with increase in the supporting electrolyte concentration.

The $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ values were of the same order indicating a shift from irreversible electrode reaction to almost reversible electrode reaction via quasi-reversible electrode reaction. The reversible half wave potentials were calculated by Gellings' method¹⁵.

According to Goto and Tachi¹⁶, if α in relation $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4} = \frac{0.0564}{\alpha n}$ is less than 0.5, the electrode process is said to be totally irreversible. In the present study, the value of α is < 0.5 upto 0.4 M potassium chloride, and > 0.5 at above 0.5 M potassium chloride while in 1.0 M potassium chloride, the wave is almost reversible. This is clear from the log plot slope value.

Koutecky's method¹⁷ as extended by Meites and Israel¹⁸ was used to calculate the kinetic parameters (α and $k_{0,r,h}$) for irreversible polarographic waves obtained in 0.1 M to 0.4 M potassium chloride (Fig. 1, a,b), whereas Gellings' method was used to evaluate kinetic parameters (α and $k_{s,h}$) for quasi-reversible waves obtained in 0.5 M to 0.9 M potassium chloride (Fig. 1, c,d). In the present study the value of $k_{s,h}$ was found to be of the order of 10^{-4} cm/sec, confirming the electrode process to be quasi-reversible¹⁹. All the polarographic data have been listed in Table 2.

All the criteria lead to a safe conclusion that for Pr(III) an irreversible polarographic wave is obtained in 0.1 M to 0.4 M potassium chloride, which attains a quasi-reversible nature, on increasing the supporting electrolyte and finally becomes a

Fig. 1. Series of polarograms of 2 mM Pr(III) + 0.01% gelatin at pH 2.4 ± 0.02 in varying concentration of KCl: (A) 0.1M, (B) 0.2M, (C) 0.5M, (D) 0.8M and (E) 1.0M.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF POTASSIUM CHLORIDE ON 2 mM Pr(III)+0.01% GELATIN AT 2.4±0.02

Concentration of KCl	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SOE	$-E'_{1/2}$ V vs SOE	$D \times 10^6$ cm/sec ²	Slope of log plot (in mV)	α	$k_{s,h}$ cm/sec	$k'_{r,h}$ cm/sec
0.1 M	1.77	—	2.74	45	0.437	—	2.4×10^{-40}
0.2 M	1.78	—	2.60	40	0.491	—	2.6×10^{-44}
0.5 M	1.785	1.7705	2.48	30	0.655	9.9×10^{-4}	—
0.8 M	1.80	1.79	2.37	25	0.790	8.3×10^{-4}	—
1.0 M	1.81	1.81	2.20	19	—	—	—

well defined almost reversible three electron reduction wave in 1.0 M potassium chloride, as was also observed by Verma *et al*⁵ in the reduction of Ni(II) in potassium thiocyanate, and also in agreement with the previously published results³. The electrode process can be explained by the simple three electron reduction as also reported in the literature².

Effect of the metal ion concentration: When varying concentrations of Pr(III) from 1 mM to 10 mM were polarographed separately in 1.0 M KCl+0.01% gelatin at pH 2.4±0.02 (Fig. 1, e), the half wave potential (-1.81 V vs SCE) was found to be independent of the metal ion concentration. The diffusion current constant was observed to be 3.55 ± 0.3 .

The observations are in contrast with those of Swenson and Glockler² who observed a negative shift in half wave potential, when more concentrated solutions of the metal ion were polarographed in lithium chloride as supporting electrolyte. The half wave potential, a characteristic property of the metal ion was found to vary with a change in the metal ion concentration, in other electrolytes. The plots of i_d vs \sqrt{t} were linear passing through the origin, indicating that the reduction of Pr(III) is diffusion controlled. The plots of wave height vs concentration of the metal ion gave a straight line passing through the origin, indicating that the diffusion current is proportional to the metal ion concentration.

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